

Examining Well-being: Lived Experiences, Individual Agency, and Epistemic Inclusion of Marginalized Voices

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The twenty-first century is witnessing a massive influx of human mobility, and India is not apart from the trend. Therefore, from a psychological perspective, we are drawn to the life associated with migration, subjective lived experiences, and the psychological process behind living, particularly when the journey reveals a distinctive story. However, migration has become a life strategy since the onset of globalization. Therefore, migration has a substantial impact on psychological health and well-being, emphasizing the need to adjust to new surroundings after relocation. The experiences of members of marginalized groups and how they maintain their sustainability in the face of various difficulties and uncertainties may be more fascinating. While many studies concentrate on temporal lives and their shortcomings on marginalization, the qualitative aspects of life and the process of negotiating or reframing life are mainly disregarded. Specifically, how migration results in a qualitative change in one's sense of self and identity, and how migrants adjust to achieve well-being. Thus, the current study seeks to investigate the lived experiences of migrants, especially those from our society's socioeconomically disadvantaged segments. Semi-structured in-depth interviews were carried out with 20 participants (The participant counts for each group are: *Bhunjawala*: 6, *Fuchkawala*: 7, and water supplier/*Bhari*: 7) to examine lived experiences and perceptions of self/identity and well-being. Four themes—dedication to God, futurization, transcendence, and sociocultural rootedness/spirituality—have emerged from the data analysis, for which Charmaz's three-layer coding of the qualitative method was followed. These themes have positively impacted their sense of well-being in life.

Keywords: Well-being, marginal life, identity/self, lived experiences

The issues related to well-being are drawing relevance in contemporary times. Human life and mobility are increasingly influenced by globalization and the postmodern society's abundance and instability, ultimately affecting the subjective experiences and various perspectives on well-being (Svasek, 2010). Human existence encompasses both temporal and qualitative aspects, with a strong link to psychological well-being, yet the latter receives insufficient attention. Life is evaluated through material and immaterial lenses, emphasizing the importance of recognizing various dimensions in research and practice. Interactions between these facets and the environment led to variations in identification methods. In this context, 'human migration' emerges as a crucial life strategy impacting millions globally, particularly in India. So, migration and its associated consequences affect people to various extents in their modern lives. Moreover, one crucial aspect of modern

life and society that alters people's identities/selves is relocation (Sheller, 2014). However, the psychological, social, and other qualitative aspects are positively correlated with one's existence or well-being. Furthermore, when a person's physical location changes, their identity, sense of belonging, and social connections are negatively connected with their psychological well-being (Flynn, 2017). The issue of marginality is linked to migration as a modern-day life strategy, with migrants facing challenges both before and after migration. These challenges, particularly for socioeconomically disadvantaged individuals, contribute to various forms of marginalization and possess psychosocial repercussions. Being separated from friends and family, having fewer possessions, adjusting to the complex environment in their new location, having few personal resources, and having little to no social support all contribute to the marginalization of migrants (Bronstein, 2019). Moreover, self-concept and identity are affected by the shift in the social support network and lifestyle patterns in the general and new mode of acculturation, assimilation, and integration into a new set of cultural regulations (Bhugra et al., 2005). Migrants' susceptibility to the new way of life, particularly the post-pandemic environment and amid various stressors, increases, leaving a lasting impact on their psychological well-being (Tanwar et al., 2021). Additionally, one experiences loneliness, alienation, stigmatization, or discrimination when migrating and leaving behind family, friends, and possessions. They also interact with newly assimilated social status, identity, and cultural subset (Bhugra, 2004). Although acculturation, integration, and further acceptance in the new society all contribute to the migrants' lives and well-being, the social environment that people are exposed to, particularly disparities in socioeconomic status and unfavorable evaluation from society, influences the disparities in

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We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

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well-being as well (Fisher, 2019). Moreover, newcomers go through several physical constraints, such as information marginalization in the new destination due to a lack of sociocultural knowledge and language proficiency, which negatively impacts migrants while fulfilling everyday needs (Hallerod & Selden, 2013). As a result of information marginalization, migrants engage in self-defense strategies like secrecy and lose faith in outsider-contextualized information sources (Bronstein, 2019). Nonetheless, a number of perceived disparities have been found in recent research to impact some intangible psychological factors, like the decision-making process. These include discrimination on the basis of sexual orientation, gender, race, or political beliefs (Charron, 2020; as cited in Zanker et al., 2023), a sense of exclusion from the mainstream (Vacchiano 2018; as cited in Zanker et al., 2023), and feelings of relative deprivation (Gereke, 2016; as cited in Zanker et al., 2023) in the host place. The experience and process of migration also entail a number of subjective internal discussions from which one can assess oneself and form opinions about oneself with the goal of promoting one's well-being.

Health and well-being are perceived differently among demographic groups due to varying sociocultural systems and a lack of cross-cultural consensus. Understanding the cultural specificity and emic perspectives is essential for grasping the concept of existence or well-being. Additionally, fostering resilience and coping strategies may significantly benefit from a spiritual sense of being. According to recent health literature, spiritual well-being should be considered in addition to biological and psychological aspects of health and well-being (Ghaderi et al., 2018; Alborzi et al., 2019; as cited in Božek, 2020). While health practices associated with improved psychological well-being may mediate the relationship between spirituality and health, moreover, the psychosocial and religious components of spiritual health are thought to be advantageous (Ghaderi et al., 2018; Alborzi et al., 2019; as cited in Božek, 2020). Empirical evidence suggests that building resilience through comprehension of life's obstacles is essential for preserving well-being (Manning et al., 2019). As a result, traditional and cultural values actively contribute to the resolution of psychosocial issues. Through a transcendental process, these take place among marginalized urban groups (Saha et al., 2024).

Additionally, the environment of a person's new place, the people there, their relationships, and the intricate dynamics of their everyday negotiation with the changing space all have a significant impact on their growing sense of self-reflection (Kelly, 2017; Ardel & Grunwald, 2018). Crucially, people act upon the meanings and connotations that they comprehend from pursuing their life in both their pre-migration and post-migration lifestyles, which means that they have the power to understand and affect reality (Rivera, 2025). Thus, the relationship with a changing environment and its psychosocial consequences varies significantly among different populations. The distinct approach to managing altered surroundings is essential for resilience. Post-migration life may not align with previous modes of interaction and leisure. For meaningful existence, individuals and communities must adapt through acculturation and integration.

Although post-migration life is accompanied by an integration and acculturation strategy, this phase entails the comprehension of the acculturative transition as a process of self-construction and empowerment whereby migrants gain a new perspective on the world and themselves, changing both the structural environment and themselves (García-Ramírez et al., 2011). In the process of self-

construction, individuals quest to reestablish their social standing and references, reassembling their personal and social assets, and attaining a new agency consistent with their new objectives and challenges towards achieving well-being. The most interesting aspect is the unique way that may evolve from the pursuit of migrant life being marginalized, which may uncover different shades of reality closer to the mainstream narrative.

Review of Literature

When people migrate, they leave behind their previous lifestyle, family, and social connections, which requires them to reestablish interactions with the host society as familiar methods become ineffective (Zabeer et al., 2019). Additionally, leisure can help migrant adults and youths develop their ethnic identities, reduce stress, boost confidence and self-esteem, and enhance life satisfaction (Monica & Stodolska, 2018). Limited time restricts the marginalized workforce's participation in leisure activities, hindering their contribution to integration. Migrants often face challenges such as living away from family, cultural barriers, and socio-economic uncertainty, especially among disadvantaged groups (Meyer et al., 2018; Li et al., 2014). Furthermore, structural discrimination worsens because of stigma against vulnerable groups, shaped by factors like occupation, social status, and neglect of power structures. The concept of marginality should include the daily resistance and psychosocial challenges faced by impoverished migrant populations in multicultural settings. A high prevalence of anxiety and psychotic disorders among migrant workers results from socio-environmental hardships, including discrimination, social isolation, and changes in social status (Mucci et al., 2019).

However, socioculturally marginalized individuals are more likely to have low self-esteem and confidence, few opportunities to contribute to society, and little control over their lives and the resources that are available to them from a community and psychological perspective (Burton & Kagan, 2003; as cited in Di Fabio & Palazzeschi, 2016). Additionally, the destination setup typically fails to address the emotional ties and identification that the underprivileged migrant population feels toward their home country. Strong ties to a location can provide social status, significance, and support, as well as aid in the development of an individual's identity and sense of belonging (Benson & Jackson, 2013). Furthermore, the disintegrating components of social disengagement, lack of psychological and transcendental cues, loss of autonomy, family separation, and little free time all work together to raise the feelings of alienation and cause distress (Saha et al., 2024).

Therefore, given the qualitative loss they have committed to the entire migration journey, one must reframe this psychologically or with the assistance of other agencies. Individual abilities and ethnic traits are regarded as significant in the integration process. Numerous studies have emphasized the significance of the host society and the various aspects of it that are linked to migrant lives (Hendriks, 2015). Research involving 1714 migrants in Spain shows that those with a stronger sense of community report worse psychosocial outcomes, emphasizing the need for social networks to enhance well-being (García-Cid et al., 2020). Additionally, a study on marginalized male migrant laborers from Bangladesh in the UAE reveals that health and well-being are influenced by cultural factors and the integration of physical and mental health within familial roles (Kumar & Jamil, 2020).

During integration, individuals undergo significant identity

changes crucial for well-being in a new society. García-Ramírez et al. (2010) and Berry (1997) highlight that cultural integration is vital for managing migration-related stress, linking coping mechanisms to the acculturation process, which requires active participation, particularly in multicultural settings.

Despite the complexity of human cognition, disagreements frequently interfere with the integration of ideas and behaviors. Self-awareness and inner harmony can be increased by upholding spiritual values, such as seeking a sense of wholeness and life purpose. In Indian spiritual life and tradition, self-awareness is the ultimate goal of spirituality (Kabat-Zinn, 1990; as cited in Kalita et al., 2025). Spirituality is a dynamic reality that is constantly learning something new through alternative perspectives (Božek et al., 2020). Finding the ultimate boundaries of existence and seeking a more profound purpose in life may also be part of it (Božek et al., 2020). Thus, the pursuit of cues that lead to self-awareness eventually results in a sense of existence.

In modern literature, spirituality and religious practices are noted as beneficial coping strategies for cancer patients. A review by Nagy et al. (2024) indicated that increased spiritual and religious coping is linked to improved treatment outcomes, lower distress, and better quality of life. Spirituality, which involves searching for meaning, supplements religious practices that provide resilience in adversity. Additional studies highlight that spirituality boosts well-being by improving awareness and aiding in stress and health management.

Method

Participants

For the current study, three participant groups were selected from three distinct marginalized groups, including bhunjawalas, fuchkawalas, and drinking water suppliers (Bhari). A total of twenty participants, including 6 Bhunjawala, 7 Fuchkawala, and 7 water suppliers/Bhari, were chosen for data collection. All participants migrated to Kolkata from other states, including Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, and Odisha. The drinking water suppliers/Bhari were an unskilled workforce who used to supply drinking water for household usage in different pockets in Kolkata and metropolitan areas. This group came from Odisha a long time ago and used to stay in rented slum areas of different pockets in Kolkata. The other two groups of *bhunjawalas* and *fuchkawalas* were unorganized groups of vendors who were vending tiffin items, especially in the evening time in different parts of Kolkata. Both these groups of participants migrated from Bihar and Uttar Pradesh and used to stay in rented accommodation in Kolkata. All the participants belong to the

unorganized group, and all of them struggled to mark their feet in the new destination. Additionally, all the participants represent their weaknesses in socioeconomic conditions and are hence marginalized in the multicultural social setup in Kolkata.

Measure

The current study intends to examine the qualitative aspects of the socioeconomically disadvantaged urban migrant group's well-being. More specifically, this study will examine the subjective well-being of different marginalized migrant worker groups from rural to urban areas with lower socioeconomic backgrounds and understand the significance of meaning in assisting the various migrant workers in transforming their identities/selves in the new sociocultural context. It will also look into the subjective experiences of marginal living in relation to their well-being.

Procedure

For the study, a purposive sampling technique was employed. Participant observation, semi-structured in-depth interviews, and field notes were used to collect data for this study. As a qualitative research tool, the study employed semi-structured in-depth interviews. Several important questions that aided in defining and comprehending the areas of investigation are included in a semi-structured in-depth interview. Additionally, open-ended questions were used to gather data, and an audio recorder was used to capture their experiences. In order to better understand the participants, participant observation notes and a photo were also taken. One by one, each participant was contacted for an interview at their self-paced time and place, and consent was taken from all of them.

Statistical Analysis

After collecting all the data, transcriptions were made, and the analysis was done following the three-layer coding of qualitative research prescribed by Charmaz (Charmaz, 2006). The references that support the application of grounded theory coding in phenomenological research were consulted (Taylor, 2015). Starting with the initial coding of each data transcription, also referred to as open coding, which entails emphasizing the dialogue excerpts from the transcription where the exception was taken from the recorded interviews. In order to identify the research's focus areas, the next step entails focused coding, with a focus on categorization and the creation of analytical codes. The coding process comes to an end when the theme or axial coding, which generates the coherence with the "emerging analysis," is determined (Charmaz, 2006).

Results

Table 1

Major Themes and Descriptions of the Themes

Themes	Descriptions of the themes
Dedication to God	They completely surrender to God; whatever good things happen to them, they interpret as God's grace, and they give up their suffering, as well.
Futurization	They put forth a lot of effort to give their children a good education and help them become well-established in the future, which gives their lives motivation and meaning.
Transcendence	During their migration journey, they engage in a psychological process of strategic thinking. Transcendence, then, is the element that enables them to reframe, regulate, and direct their emotions in achieving both identity and well-being.
Sociocultural rootedness & spirituality	Regularly, they perform their worship to Lord Jagannath or Anukul Thakur before leaving for work, and besides that, they traditionally celebrate and take part in the rituals according to their convenience at their native place. Additionally, they pray to God for uplifting in life and the common good for all, which shows their sociocultural rootedness and spirituality.

Discussion

From the present study, four themes have emerged: Dedication to the god, futurization, transcendence, sociocultural rootedness, and spirituality. The perspective of the marginalized groups distinctively shaped the themes that emerged, and the understanding that they gain from this experience may lead to a new sense of what it means to be well-being. However, all the themes are interconnected and reflected in socioculturally ingrained ways.

The findings and analysis show that, while attaining a sense of well-being, the perspective of self from the marginal position in the multicultural society and the importance of meaning in transforming the "self" as a migrant differ. The sociocultural and spiritual roots of the groups under study regulate and navigate the importance of meaning in attaining well-being. Participants with that agency are said to be able to make sense of their lives and eventually navigate them meaningfully, to attain well-being.

The experiences that the members of the Bhari, Fuchkawala, and Bhunjawala group shared are fascinating as they depicted themselves within the framework of a distinct society. They have articulated negotiation, resistance, resilience-building, and redefined how one navigates sustainability in a unique way. Despite having experienced social exploitation, discrimination for being marginalized, and a lack of professional organization in handling issues, the participants are powerless at work. However, structural discrimination, a lack of political representation, and exploitation are commonplace for marginalized migrant workers from India (Faetanini & Tankha, 2013; as cited in Suresh et al., 2020).

Dedication to God

Furthermore, especially during the acculturation process, individual capability frequently functions as an agency while coping with all the emotional and physical challenges. Through a transcendental journey, the crucial element of having sociocultural and spiritual rootedness influences many facets of life resistance after migration. Similarly, one could consider the transcendental process of explaining life to be an existential phenomenon that a person experiences under particular conditions (Salagame, 2016).

"With the blessings of Lord Jagannath - "Thakur" no such bad incident happened here so far. I am here keeping away my son, daughter, and my wife. After coming here from the country, I am fine. With the blessings of Jagannath, I am fine".

I: Can you observe anything here, as you are a disciple of "Thakur Anukul," the benevolent master?

P: "Whenever there is an event or festival, there is no time with us to go. Any of us will go and join, that's difficult; it is not our time. We confess that "Thakur" we do not have time, it is not possible. What will be observed will be done in our native home later. There is nothing to do here."

I: How long will you do it?

P: "As long as the blessings of "Jagannath" are there, the blessings of "Thakur", the blessings of parents are possible."- Participant D.B

The majority of participants from the Bhari, Bhunjawala, and Fuchkawala groups described their experiences in a way that illustrates their devotion to God and even demonstrates their sociocultural and spiritual rootedness; additionally, pictures of Lord Jagannath and Anukul Thakur are also kept in their disorganized room. Therefore, it is clear that cultivating resilience through

devotion and having faith in Lord Jagannath/God leads to spirituality, which ultimately helps them make sense of existence in the host social world. Numerous examples from anthropological research demonstrate that religious practice is a component of culture and social values, and that spirituality embedded in specific cultural experiences and values is a way for people to express their spirituality (Edara, 2017). The spiritual pathway helps people deal with psychological issues and make sense of their experiences by utilizing socioreligious and culturally ingrained aspects of values and practice. However, Ramsay et al. (2019) suggested that those who are positively engaged in religion and spirituality—that is, who believe that a higher power is guiding and connecting them—tend to have more positive views or motivation about their lives. Members of these groups are likely to be able to seek inner congruence by using the spiritual pathway and navigate their thoughts accordingly.

Futurization

The participants have been able to relate to reality and have accepted the deep connection to their former lives. They are able to relate the experiences of their ancestors and their sociocultural roots to their life journey. They have described how they see their current efforts in the host location serving a higher purpose. Interestingly, the participants who belong to the Bhari, Fuchkawala, and Bhunjawala groups involve themselves in futurization to a greater sense. Providing better education for children, making their careers, or positioning their children in better jobs, and building a concrete home are the thoughts they continuously revolve around.

"Yes, I have a dream that I will give my son and daughter a good education. I have left them, my daughter just wrote the Madhyamik exam, and on the eighteenth, her result will be published. I hope she will achieve 500/550 marks, then I will put her in a good college. Expenses may be increased, which is why I am working hard here. If she continues with good results and gets a good job, then our sufferings will be over. She will understand how her father works hard and sends money for her, staying away from home. So, I will give him rest from studying hard. That is continuing in my mind. That is our dream."- Participant D.B

Almost all of the participants have dreamt about that. Earning money solely for fulfilling desires or earning just for livelihood is not the case for the marginalized participants. They futurize their efforts in the workplace by having a wide sense of purpose and thinking about the betterment of their course of life instead of fulfilling raw materialistic desires. This idea, though, might have its origins in their social and familial backgrounds. They most likely justify their suffering by assuming that the following generation will look after them in their later years and that they will be able to carry on their family's legacy. It's interesting to note how they meaningfully craft their story of suffering in life, suggesting that it may eventually end and that they will live a happy life. A study found that migrants' perceptions of the future show up when assessing their sense of social well-being and their awareness of the current situation in relation to their self-futurization (Blaginina & Ergunova, 2018).

However, they have perceived their success as they have justified their journey of relocation by futurizing their current endeavor.

"I dreamt of building my own home, the then it was built of mud, I have completed it, and that was my wish. Children will be happy, and we all will have the same, that is the expectation. I did not regret it for life. With the blessing of Thakur Anukul and my

parents, I think that my family is doing well. I am not a salaried man; whatever I get with the blessing, I am fine, that is my peace. I will look after my family, my children, and my home with that. I will take care of my relations with others, that is my wish.”- Participant S.B

Transcendence - Sociocultural/Spiritual Rootedness

By bringing life's essence to the path, a sense of life, a connection to a transcendent force, and a sense of connection with others enable them to eventually navigate into a meaningful journey. The post-migrant life always struggles to positively adapt to the host environment and thus migrants are involved in adopting coping mechanisms and resilience building. Additionally, their ability to deal with life's obstacles and make sense of their existence is made possible by sociocultural and spiritual agency, which gives them a stronger sense of purpose and rationale for migrating. It is thought that spiritual health's psychosocial and religious components are advantageous (Ghaderi et al., 2018; Alborzi et al., 2019; as cited in Božek, 2020). However, spirituality and health may be mediated by health-related behaviors that are also associated with enhanced psychological well-being. Additionally, studies show that spirituality predicts psychological well-being more accurately than behavioral factors (Park et al., 2009; Unterrainer et al., 2014).

“It means that the mind will never be calm. There are two things in this body: a soul and a mind, the mind is the devil, and the soul is the human being. I sit down to drink wine, and when the glass comes to my mouth, the voice comes from inside. it is not a good thing. There is another thing that is in my mind, that says I bring this wine to drink, so why don't we drink? But whenever I drink, my mind will be weak. So, the soul is great.”- Participant R.C.P

In addition to regularly praying to Lord Jagannath and chanting mantras in a peaceful manner, they have stated that they have dedicated their lives to "Lord Jagannath/God" or "Thakur Anukul." This indicates that they are involved in religious activities that likely help them stay psychologically connected to their religious and cultural heritage through transcendental ways.

“Religious observation means that in the morning, there is a rule to perform prayer in the morning and evening, but we cannot perform it in the evening, as we do not get time. Only in the morning, after getting up and washing our face and hands, chant the ista jop (mantra). Then, after pranam, we get out for work. In our native home, we perform puja in a grand manner, and many people are invited to have prasad. People will come, meet with each other, and have prasad together. My elder sister, members of my in-laws' house, and my friends will come, and we will enjoy ourselves a lot. Here we don't have this.”- Participant D.B

Participants still uphold the family and social network that their forefathers established, which may allow them to stay in touch with one another. Even though they have trouble enjoying their leisure time, their psychological well-being is unaffected. Probably spirituality creates a bridge to cope with the daily challenges. A grounded theory analysis shows that when dealing with late-life challenges, spirituality is used as a tool to promote resilience and preserve well-being (Manning et al., 2019).

As a result, the three group members' perspectives, based on their personal experiences, are focused on attaining well-being and constructive coping. Their coping strategies throughout their life's

journey reveal their spiritual and sociocultural roots. Ardel et al. (2008) claim that spirituality is a part of resilience because it provides a framework for overcoming life's challenges and separating the positive from the negative. Spirituality is defined as the search for a deeper meaning in life and existence, which can lead to happiness and a positive outlook on life. A sense of self, meaning, and inner harmony can result from adhering to spiritual principles, such as having a purpose in life, feeling one with others and nature, and being whole (Heintzman, 2000). Despite their differences, religion and spirituality are deeply ingrained in social values and cultural aspects, and they frequently influence people's daily mental processes. It is clear that the various facets of culture and religion serve as a unifying factor, which is a normal occurrence. However, when one is connected to and involved with the higher power, the cognitive aspect of subjective well-being always assesses oneself and makes favorable assessments. However, engaging in religious activities provides a means of expressing one's spirituality, which likely helps one adapt to the circumstances (Nagy et al., 2024). A qualitative study of Spanish immigrants found that religion and spirituality are closely related and have a big impact on how the immigrants interpret their experiences. Both significant life events and routine activities lead to the creation of meaning and different types of spirituality, both religious and nonreligious ways. In the end, it contributes to positive well-being by providing a sense of community, values, and purpose (Spännäri & Laceulle, 2021).

Conclusion

The subjective experiences and the anecdote of everyday negotiation with the environment by the marginalized urban groups revealed unique accounts of the pursuit of well-being. The current study sought to investigate the course of achieving well-being, and the study's participants offered a distinctive perspective on the broad phenomenon of well-being and its maintenance in a multicultural host society. Their psychological functioning toward adjustments grounded on spirituality and sociocultural rootedness and personal agency distinctively contributed and marked their path, even though they faced temporal challenges that led to marginalization or relative differences in the host society. Moreover, the lived experiences of the marginal living surface the optimization of the strategy to be resilient and ultimately become able to reframe their life towards having a greater sense of self/identity and well-being. Therefore, the marginalized perspectives of life sought academic attention to be recognized by the field of research and practice as well as society. While acknowledging and embracing a comprehensive understanding of the concept of well-being, further research on the qualitative perspective of the construct “well-being” is highly encouraged.

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Received December 17, 2025

Revision received January 5, 2026

Accepted January 8, 2026